
Rice Production in Doma Local Government Area, Nasarawa State 1996-2023

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ABSTRACT	ARTICLE DETAILS
<p>The paper provides a historical document on rice production in Doma Local Government Area, Nasarawa State from 1996-2023. Rice is important in Nigeria for several reasons. It is a staple for most of the peoples in the country and a major contributor to internal and sub-regional trade. The understanding by Doma farmers that rice can easily be cultivated in area with low soil fertility and its huge array of varieties encourages them to continue to cultivate rice no matter the constraints faced. Rice production level before now have not been able to achieve stability despite the huge capital injection from World Bank loans to myriads of government's interventionist programmes since 1966. This is due to poor management of water resources and irrigation system in the area, farmers' inability to access credit facilities, inability to improved seed varieties, low farm inputs and low patronage of agro allied chemicals. Despite these challenges, rice production continues to assumes salient agricultural activity in Doma contributing significantly to food security and economic livelihood of the people. However, the thrust of this paper is on hectares of land cultivated, production levels in metric tonnes and yield production in metric tonnes per hectare. The paper adopts agricultural development theory using resource exploitation and location models emphasising increase in agricultural potential in driving economic growth, reduce poverty, and improve food security, particularly in developing countries. This paper argues that, the recent upsurge in rice production is attributed to the presence of Olam company cultivating over ten thousand hectares, the introduction of Olam's nucleus out growers scheme in 2012, the rise of farm settlement across Doma attracting migrant labours from different parts of the country and the adequate uses of agro allied chemicals. The paper adopts multi-disciplinary approach based on historical method of using both primary and secondary sources of data. Collected data were qualitatively analysed.</p>	<p>Published On: 09 May 2026</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Agricultural Production, Rice, and Rice Production</p>	<p>Available on: https://ijiissh.com/</p>

INTRODUCTION

Doma is by far one of the highest rice producing local governments in Nasarawa State due to the presence of the Olam company located in Rukubi. It's a multi-ethnic and culturally diverse enclave hosting Algo as the major ethnic group, followed by Agatu, Tiv, Egon, Migili, and Bassa. It has ten electoral wards and two hundred and fourteen electoral polling units. The ten electoral wards include Alagye, Rukubi, Agbashi, Doka, Akpanaja, Madaki, Sarki-Dawaki, Madauchi, Galadima, and Sabo-Gari electoral wards. The area has been recognised as the largest rice-producing local government with over 10,000 hectares under Olam company's cultivation. Although, some progress has been made in socio-economic terms in recent years, but serious social, economic, and security challenges caused by communal clashes, rising banditry related attacks, and kidnapping threaten food security as they hinder access to farms for food production, especially rice production.¹

Indeed, the area has the highest numbers of farming communities from different parts of the State. The establishment of several farm settlements in different locations of the local government which includes Agbanoko, Omadugu, Samunaka, Baki-Kasa, and Ajewoni were aimed at producing bumper harvest. In these settlements, farmers spent several months from January to November, a harvest period before returning home. Anko, a pioneer on migrant labours to the West otherwise called Kurmi argues that, the establishment of farm settlements and communities ended the aged-long migration movement experienced by the people

¹ C. Angwam, "Nasarawa Begins Harvest of 10,000 Hectares of Rice Farm." *The Punch*, 26 May, 2024

to the Western part of the country in late 19th century. The mass exodus of people from neighbouring states of plateau, Taraba Jos and Kaduna became catalyst to high agricultural production specially rice. To him, the migrant labours worked for a paid job such as clearing, cultivation, weeding harvesting and conveying of crops home. Some exchanged their labours with proceed of harvested crops.²

Another reason for high production of rice in the local government is the introduction and adequate application of agro-allied chemicals such as fertilisers of different kinds. The fertilisers provide essential nutrients, enhancing soil fertility and promoting healthy crop growth, leading to higher yields. Agro-allied chemicals help control weeds, preventing competition for water and nutrients, resulting in better quality rice. On the other hand, pesticides protect crops from damaging pests and diseases, reducing losses and ensuring a healthier harvest. A user of agro-allied chemicals, Anza, describes how effective and efficient are the chemicals and how it has aided to high production of rice in Doma, when he said, farmers cultivated large hectares in the 21st century due to availability of agro-allied chemicals. He went further say, land cultivated by extended family members in 20th century could be cultivated by single farmers. At times, farming was done through a popular 'zero system' where herbicides were spread twice before planting crops without cultivation making the system more economical.³

However, the establishment of Olam's 'nucleus outgrowers' scheme in Rukubi, Doma local government from 2012 received a boost in rice production using outgrowers' production, attracting subsidies on the cost of improved seed variety, training (i.e. knowledge transfers on various aspects of rice production and agricultural best practices), and extension services. In return, outgrowers are expected to sell their output to Olam at market-determined prices. These terms are included in the written agreement that outgrowers' assent prior to engagement in the scheme and become reasons for maximum rice production.⁴

Rice is a staple food in Nigeria, playing critical roles in food security and economic stability. With the country's growing population and increasing demand for rice, the dynamics in rice production are essential for informing policy decisions and interventions, which this seminar paper aims to provide: a comprehensive analysis of rice production in Doma local government, with emphasis on factors that have influenced its growth and development over time. However, to cope with the growing population in the state, its great agricultural potential needs attention to enable the sector meets the nutritional demands.⁵

This, no doubt, explains the government's aggressive policies towards agricultural sector, rice inclusive, in different states of the federation since 1966. From huge injections of capital through World Bank loans to myriads of programmes and interventions such as Operation Feed the Nation (OFN, 1976), National Accelerated Food Production Project (NAFPP, 1975), Green Revolution (1979), Back to Land (1984), Directorates for Food Roads and Rural Infrastructures (DFRRI, 1985), Better Life for Rural Women (1986), National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA, 1992), Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP, 1994), National Agricultural Research Project (NARP, 1995), the Special Rice Project (SRP, 1998), National Fadama Development Project (NFDP, 1999), the Nigerian National Rice Development Strategy (NRDS), set up in 2009 to increase the production of paddy rice from 3.4 million tonnes in 2007 to 12.8 million tonnes in 2018. Also, the Presidential Initiative on rice implemented from 2001 to 2007 centred on developing rice production, processing, and exports. Other government efforts aimed at encouraging the local production of rice were contained in the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) policy This policy was not only aimed at making Nigeria self-sufficient in rice production by 2017 but also aimed to treats agriculture as a business rather than a development project.⁶

In spite of this huge attention, the problem remains inability to deliver improved agricultural technologies to farmers, limited extension resources, low inputs, managerial and infrastructural failure, inadequate and inconsistent policy implementation due to frequent changes in governments. In addendum, agricultural inputs have continued to be very expensive and thus, unavailable to farmers even in the current democratic dispensation. The paper discusses the following themes: introduction, conceptual and theoretical framework, history of rice in Nigeria, analysis of rice in Doma local government area from 1996-2023, economic importance of rice to Doma societies, and conclusion.⁷

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

² Anko Shaibu, Oral Interview, Farmer, Doma LGA, Nasarawa State, April 24th, 2025.

³ Paul Anza, Oral Interview, Civil Servant/ Farmer, Doma, Nasarawa State, 15TH January, 2025.

⁴ S. Terwase, "Economic Impact of Olam Out-Grower Programme on Rice Farming in Kaambe District of Guma Local Government, Benue State, Nigeria." *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* Vol. 1 No. 17 (2011), 303.

⁵ Africa Rice Centre, "Rice Seed Production Techniques: Investing in Rural People." Retrieved from www.AfricaRiceCenter.org.org. Accessed on May 16, 2025

⁶ S. Fatai Abiola, and O. Dammy Abegunrin. "Profit Efficiency of The Rice Milling Industry and Sustainability of the Rice Value Chain in Nigeria." Available at <https://www.jstor.org>. Accessed on 4 July, 2025.

⁷ S. R. Longtau, *Multi-Agency Partnerships in West African Agriculture: A Review and Description of Rice Production Systems in Nigeria*. Nigeria: WIS Partners Press, 2003, 4.

Agricultural Production

F. Ellis (1993, p.453) described agricultural “production as the output of goods produced by farming, including food, fiber, biofuels, and raw materials, through the cultivation of plants and the rearing of animals, measured by yield per unit of input.” The Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) cited in World Bank (2013, p.45-55) viewed agricultural production as the process of transforming natural resources, including land, water, and biodiversity into food, fiber, and fuel through cultivation, harvesting, and animal husbandry. Furthermore, agricultural production encompasses the cultivation of plants and the raising of animals, transforming inputs such as seeds, fertilisers, and labour into outputs like food, raw materials, and animal products. To George, et al (2019, 10-17), agricultural production refers to the systematic process of using land, labour, and capital to produce food and other goods for human consumption through crop cultivation, livestock farming, and related activities. This study defines agriculture as the cultivation of crops and rearing of animals for man’s consumption.

Rice production

Jones, in Longtau’s work “Multi-Agency Partnerships in West African Agriculture: A Review and Description of Rice Production Systems in Nigeria 2003,” argues that rice is a staple for most of the people in Nigeria. He argues that, three types of rice are cultivated in Nigeria. These are the African rice, *Oryza glaberrima*; Asian rice, *Oryza sativa*; and only recently, WARDA's hybrid rice, NERICA, available only to farmers under WARDA's PVS program. He further says, modern rice varieties are FARO 44(Sipi), FARO 14, FARO 7, DA 29, Mai Adda, BKN, IR 54, MAS-2401, FARO 36, 37, 27, 29, and 15. Other local varieties cultivated in Nigeria over time include Kaura, Danboto, Farin irin, Jan irin, Baki irin, and Yar liman. For Jones, the African rice *Oryza glaberrima* originated from the wild rice *Oryza barthii* some 3500 years ago, and its offspring were domesticated probably in the inland delta area of the Niger, from where it spread through the upper Niger valley to the rest of West Africa. African rice is cultivated both as a field crop and as a paddy crop.⁸

In a work titled “Rice Seed Production Techniques: Investing in Rural People 2001” by the Africa Rice Centre stressed that, the potential land for rice production in Nigeria is about five million hectares. Out of this, only about 1.8 million hectares, or 35 percent of the available land areas, are presently cropped to rice. The main production ecologies for rice in Nigeria are rain-fed lowland, rain-fed upland, irrigated lowland, deep water/floating, and mangrove swamp. Of these, rain-fed lowland rice has the largest share of the rice area (50%) and rice production.⁹

Rice production in Nigeria is constrained by several factors, which include poor access to quality seed of improved rice varieties, inappropriate technologies, poor supply of inputs, ineffective farmer organisations and groups, poor marketing arrangements, inconsistent government policies, and environmental constraints. Of these constraints, poor access to quality seed of improved rice varieties is a major limitation to quality rice production in Nigeria. The low-quality seed production is an upshot of a lack of technical power in the production of high-quality seed, inadequate land preparation, poor maintenance of seed fields, inadequate water management strategy, a low weed control mechanism, a poor pest control approach, and inadequate soil management practices.¹⁰

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The paper adopts agricultural development theory using resource exploitation and location models, outlining various agricultural development models focusing on the role of agriculture in economic development, emphasising agricultural potential to drive economic growth, reduce poverty, and improve food security, particularly in developing countries. Proponents of this theory include Johann Heinrich von Thunen, John Mellor, Esther Boserup, and Walt Rostow. These theories emphasised agriculture as vital for economic development, especially in rural areas, and improving agricultural productivity and efficiency as crucial for increasing output and incomes. In applying new technologies and practices, the development of effective institutions, policies, and infrastructure are catalysts to productivity and competitiveness.¹¹

The resource exploitation model stressed that, for many years, expansion in the areas cultivated or grazed has been the main means of increasing agricultural production. For example, the opening up of new lands or continents by the Westerners during the 18th and 19th centuries became important sources of food, markets, and raw materials in Europe. The model suggests that an increase in agricultural production occurs as a result of expansion in the area cultivated. The model assumes that surplus land and labour capacity will enable peasant producers to expand production rapidly under the stimulus of new markets even if they have

⁸ S. R. Longtau, *Multi-Agency Partnerships in West African Agriculture: A Review and Description of Rice Production Systems in Nigeria*. Nigeria: WIS Partners Press, 2003, 4.

⁹ Africa Rice Centre, “Rice Seed Production Techniques: Investing in Rural People.” Retrieved from www.AfricaRiceCenter.org.org. Accessed on May 16, 2025.

¹⁰ Africa Rice Centre, “Rice Seed Production...24.

¹¹ E. Boserup, *The Conditions of Agricultural Growth: The Economics of Agrarian Change under Population Pressure*. Chicago: Aldine Publishing Company, 1965, 124.

poor technology. The strength of the model is that it is applicable only in those few areas where new lands are still available. Its weakness includes the problem of how to generate growth in land and labour productivity when the slack resulting from underutilised natural resources has been exhausted. In addition, the model has a limited applicability in the third world today, as there are very few countries with surplus land, and most of the surplus lands are unsuitable for agriculture. Lastly, agricultural growth based on the model is not sustainable over the long run.¹²

Location theory model was proposed by Johann Heinrich von Thunen in 1826; this theory explains the spatial distribution of agricultural land use based on transportation costs to markets. It suggests that farmers choose locations for their farms based on proximity to markets, with the most valuable crops being produced closest to the market. The model was initially formulated to explain geographic variations in the location and intensity of agricultural production in an industrialised economy. The major assumption here is that urbanisation determines the location. The model has limited application in poor countries where a major problem is to initiate and accelerate economic growth at a sufficient rate to absorb the growing labour force rather than the geographic distribution of economic activity, and the technology necessary for the rapid agricultural growth is not available. In addition, the pathological growth of urban centres resulting from population inflow from rural areas is running in the demand for non-farm workers. However, while there is some concern in industrial location, the model has much more significant implications for agricultural development.¹³

It is the thrust of this seminar paper to look at the contending perspectives of rice production in Doma, Nasarawa State providing a framework to the understanding of how rice is produced per hectares yearly.

History of Rice in Nigeria

In spite of available literature on the origin of rice, Haredcastle argues that the major rice type grown in Nigeria includes Asian rice, *Oryza sativa*, but the exact zone of its domestication remains uncertain, although it is certainly South east Asia. Recent studies suggested that it may have been domesticated twice, once in India and once in China, corresponding to the Indica and Japonica races. However, classical sources suggest that it had been cultivated in Mesopotamia and Persia by the 2nd century BC. Unlike its African relative, *Oryza glaberrima*, Asian rice has a relatively short history in Africa. In the 13th and 14th centuries rice is reported on the East African coast via two entry routes into Nigeria. For instance, it was believed that Portuguese traders introduced Asian rice from East Africa to West Africa some 450 years ago. This is evidenced in the Portuguese 'word 'arroz' being incorporated as a loanword in many languages of West Africa. To some scholars, it could have also spread across the Sahara to northern Nigeria via the oases during the Trans-Saharan trade.¹⁴

To Williamson, the history of rice cultivation assigned the spread of Asian rice to Abeokuta in the 1850s through missionary activities in the Lagos area of Epe and Okitipupa; to the Ogoja and Abakaliki provinces after the Second World War in the 1970s; to the Shaki area of Oyo State in 1945; to the Niger Delta area in the early 1960s; and to the Ogbomosho area in 1954. For him, western Nigeria played an important role in the introduction of Asian rice in Nigeria. About a hundred years later, Asian rice has replaced the African rice in many places in Nigeria except for the deep-flooded plains of the Sokoto-Rima basin and other isolated pockets of deep swamps in the Kamodugu-Yobe drainage system and the Niger-Benue trough.¹⁵

Jones emphatically stressed that three types of rice are cultivated in Nigeria. These are the African rice, *Oryza glaberrima*; Asian rice, *Oryza sativa*; and only recently, the West African Rice Development Association's (WARDA) hybrid rice, NERICA, available only to farmers under the West African Rice Development Association's program. According to Jones, the African rice *Oryza glaberrima* originated from the wild rice *Oryza barthii* some 3500 years ago, and its offspring were domesticated probably in the inland delta area of the Niger, from where it spread through the upper Niger valley to the rest of West Africa. African rice is cultivated both as a field crop and as a paddy crop. For the Niger-Benue trough, Sokoto-Rima, and Chad Basin, rice has been in cultivation long enough for a rice culture to have evolved, going as far back as 1500 BC. Remarkable deep-water varieties of *Oryza glaberrima* existed and are specific to the unusual flood conditions that occur in the inland Niger Delta, the Sokoto-Rima Valley and other floodplains of the extreme north of Nigeria. It is also a common rice type on the floodplains of the Benue trough.¹⁶

The story of rice in West Africa is becoming more interesting in view of the technological breakthrough in the development of hybrid rice by WARDA and other partnership organisations in Africa. The rice interspecific hybridisation project has produced

¹² E. Villanueva, "What are the Theories of Agriculture?" Available at <http://www.agriculturelore.com>. Accessed on 4 July, 2025.

¹³ M. A. Katundu, *Theories of Agricultural Development*. Tanzania: Moshi Co-operative University, 2016, 10.

¹⁴ J. E.Y. Hardcastle, "The Development of Rice Production and Research in the Federation of Nigeria." *Journal of Tropical Agriculture* Vol.2 No. 5 (1959): 36.

¹⁵ Williamson, K. "Some food plant names in the Niger Delta." *International Journal of American Linguistics*, (1970): 156-167.

¹⁶ S. R. Longtau, *Multi-Agency Partnerships in West African Agriculture: A Review and Description of Rice Production Systems in Nigeria*. Nigeria: WIS Partners Press, 2003, 4.

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NERICA (New Rice for Africa). We are literally at the verge of a rice revolution in Africa as WARDA's Participatory Varietal Selections and Community Seed Production programs become full-blown. NERICA is a progeny that exhibits a hybrid vigour that has the advantages of both *Oryza glaberrima* and *Oryza sativa*, surpassing both in many regards. The revolution will be delayed unless this improved agricultural technology is delivered to farmers in a package that addresses uncertain climatic conditions, limited extension resources, and low or absent inputs.¹⁷

Judith's paper examines the cultural origins of rice cultivation in the United States, arguing that its appearance in South Carolina with the settlement of the colony (slaves) from 1670 is an African knowledge system that was transferred across the Middle Passage of slavery. The origins of this wetland farming system are explored in relation to other ethnic groups found in the colony at the time: the English, French Huguenots, and Native Americans. The paper further argues that the origin of rice production should be seen from the lens of innovators from West Africa's extensive rice-growing regions rather than slaves. However, the final section addresses the significance of gendered practices in African rice cultivation and processing and the role of female knowledge systems in the crop's diffusion across the Atlantic basin to South Carolina.¹⁸

Analysis of Rice Production in Doma since 1996-2023

According to Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, the State is one of the thirty-six states of the federation having good records of rice production, with ten thousand hectares of rice farms located in the Jangwa community of the Awe Local Government Area of the state. According to the governor, Eng. A. A. Sule, due to the improved variety of rice, the crop would be cultivated twice a year. He noted that the project was in line with the Renewed Hope Initiative of President Bola Tinubu's administration aimed at tackling hunger in the country.¹⁹

In addition, the Olam company located in Rukubi, Doma Local Government has 10,000 hectares of land fully mechanized, supplying growing domestic demand while supporting economic and agricultural development opportunities for local farmers. Indeed, the area has the highest numbers of farming communities attracting migrant labours from different parts of the State. The establishment of several farm settlements in different locations of the local government which includes Amaku, Agbanoko, Omadugu, Samunaka, Baki-Kasa, and Ajewoni were aimed at producing bumper harvest. In these settlements, farmers spent several months from January to November, a harvest period before returning home. Anko, A pioneer on migrant labours to the West otherwise called Kurumi argues that, the establishment of farm settlements and communities ended the aged-long migration movement experienced by the people to the Western part of the country in late 19th century popularly known as Kurumi. The mass exodus of people from neighbouring states of plateau, Taraba Jos and Kaduna became catalyst to high production of rice. To him, the migrant labours worked for a paid job such as clearing, cultivation, weeding harvesting and conveying of crops home. Some exchanged their labours with proceed of harvested crops.²⁰

Another reason for high production of rice in Doma is the introduction of different agro-allied chemicals such as fertilisers and herbicides. The fertilisers provide essential nutrients, enhancing soil fertility and promoting healthy crop growth, leading to higher yields. Agro-allied chemicals help control weeds, preventing competition for water and nutrients, resulting in better quality rice. Pesticides protect crops from damaging pests and diseases, reducing losses and ensuring a healthier harvest. A user of agro-allied chemicals, Paul Anza, describes how effective and efficient are the chemicals and how it has aided to high production of rice in Doma, when he said, farmers cultivated large hectares in the 21st century due to availability of agro-allied chemicals. He went further to say, land cultivated by extended family members in 80's could be cultivated by single farmers. At times, farming was done through a popular 'zero system' where herbicides were spread twice before planting crops without cultivation.²¹

The table below provides accurate data and interpretation of rice production in Doma Local Government Area:

Table 1: Rice Production from 1996-2000

S/N	Crop	Year	Area (HA) '000	Production (MT) '000	Yield (MT/HA)
1	Rice (Paddy)	1996-1997	7.55	15.19	2.01
2	Rice (Paddy)	1998	7.26	14.74	2.03
3	Rice (Paddy)	1999	6.06	13.67	2.29
4	Rice (Paddy)	2000	5.33	12.52	2.35

Source: Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, 2024.

From above, seven thousand five hundred and fifty hectares were cultivated from 1996 to 1997. Likewise, seven thousand two hundred and sixty hectares were cultivated in 1998, showing a slight decrease in cultivated areas to a 3.8% reduction. The

¹⁷ WARDA, "Technology Generation and Dissemination: The Role of Agroecological Characterization." WARDA Annual Report, Bouaké, 1999, 23-31.

¹⁸ C. Judith. "The African Origins of Carolina Rice Culture." Available at <http://www.jstor.org>. Accessed on 6 June, 2025.

¹⁹ C. Angwam, "Nasarawa Begins Harvest of 10,000 Hectares of Rice Farm." *The Punch*, 26 May, 2024.

²⁰ Anko Shaibu, Oral Interview, Farmer, Doma LGA, Nasarawa State, April 24th, 2025.

²¹ Paul Anza, Oral Interview, Civil Servant/ Farmer, Doma, Nasarawa State, 15TH January, 2025.

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production also declines from fifteen thousand one hundred and ninety metric tonnes in 1996-1997 to fourteen thousand seven hundred and forty metric tonnes in 1998, representing a 2.96% decrease in total rice production, which aligns with the reduction in cultivated area. However, improvement in yield from 2.01 metric tonnes per hectare in 1996-1997 to 2.03 metric tonnes per hectare in 1998 shows a 0.99% increase. This improvement in yield suggests that productivity per hectare remained stable, despite the reduction in the cultivated area.²²

More so, rice was cultivated on six thousand sixty hectares in 1999, producing thirteen thousand six hundred and seventy metric tonnes. Consequently, the cultivated area further decreased to five thousand three hundred and thirty hectares in 2000, implying a 12% reduction from the previous year, producing twelve thousand five hundred and twenty metric tonnes, a decrease of 8.4%. From these results, it is understood that reduction in production is linked to the decline in the cultivated area and method of farming used by farmers. However, improvement in yield shifted from 2.29 metric tonnes per hectare to 2.35 metric tonnes per hectare with an increase of 2.6% from 1999 to 2000. This indicates that while less land was used for rice cultivation, productivity per hectare improved, likely due to change in climate, better farming techniques, improved seed varieties, or favourable climatic conditions.²³

Table 2: Rice Production from 2001-2006

S/N	Crop	Year	Area (HA) '000	Production (MT) '000	Yield (MT/HA)
5	Rice (Paddy)	2001	4.020	10.17	2.15
6	Rice Paddy	2002	4.74	10.19	2.53
7	Rice (Paddy)	2003	5.35	11.06	2.17
8	Rice (Paddy)	2004	6.04	15.11	2.50
9	Rice (Paddy)	2005	6.68	15.36	2.30
10	Rice (Paddy)	2006	5.55	13.18	2.38

Source: Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, 2024.

Table two from above shows that, in 2001, rice was cultivated on four thousand twenty hectares, while, in 2002, four thousand seven hundred and forty hectares were also cultivated. The implication of the above chart is that there was an expansion of seven hundred and twenty (720) hectares, representing about 18% increase in the area under cultivation. In 2001, production was ten thousand one hundred and seventy metric tonnes. However, the 2002 production increased to ten thousand one hundred and ninety metric tonnes. Despite the increase in area, total production increased only marginally (by 0.02 thousand metric tonnes, or 20 metric tonnes), indicating a plateau in output, while yield improved from 2.15 metric tonnes per hectare of land in 2001 to 2.53 metric tonnes per hectare of land in 2002.²⁴

Again, the area cultivated increased from five thousand three hundred and fifty hectares in 2003 to six thousand forty hectares in 2004. Meaning, there is an increase of about 12.9%, implying total production rose from eleven thousand sixty metric tonnes in 2003 to fifteen thousand one hundred and ten metric tonnes in 2004, showing a 36.6% increase. While yield (productivity) improved from 2.17 metric tonnes per hectare of land in 2003 to 2.50 metric tonnes per hectare of land in 2004, a 15.2% increase in productivity per hectare. In a nutshell, between 2003 and 2004, rice cultivation expanded in area, production increased significantly, and yield per hectare also improved, suggesting better agricultural practices, improved seed varieties, or favourable growing conditions.²⁵

In 2005, six thousand six hundred and eighty hectares were cultivated and five thousand five hundred and fifty hectares were cultivated in 2006, showing a decrease of 16.9%. The total production also declined from fifteen thousand three hundred and sixty metric tonnes in 2005 to thirteen thousand one hundred and eighty metric tonnes in 2006, a reduction of about 14.2%. However, productivity increased slightly from 2.30 metric tonnes per hectare in 2005 but decreased to 2.38 metric tonnes per hectare in 2006. Despite cultivating less land in 2006, the productivity per hectare improved compared to 2005, suggesting more efficient farming practices, better inputs, and improved seedlings and crop management are factors.²⁶

Table 3: Rice Production from 2007-2012

S/N	Crop	Year	Area (HA) '000	Production (MT) '000	Yield (MT/HA)
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²² B. J. Ewuga, Oral Interview, Chief Evaluation, Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, 16TH February, 2025.

²³ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Nasarawa State Crop Production 1996-2023*. NADP: 2024, 8.

²⁴ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Nasarawa State Crop Production 1996-2023*. NADP: 2024, 8.

²⁵ B. J. Ewuga, Oral Interview, Chief Evaluation, Lafia, Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, 16TH February, 2025.

²⁶ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Nasarawa State Crop Production 1996-2023*. NADP: 2024, 8.

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11	Rice (Paddy)	2007	5.30	11.66	2.20
12	Rice (Paddy)	2008	4.88	10.79	2.21
13	Rice (Paddy)	2009	9.17	16.32	1.78
14	Rice (Paddy)	2010	12.47	34.21	2.74
15	Rice (Paddy)	2011	13.40	30.43	2.27
16	Rice (Paddy)	2012	9.83	20.02	2.04

Source: Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, 2024.

The table above shows that five thousand thirty hectares in 2007 were cultivated and four thousand eight hundred and eighty hectares in 2008. This significantly shows that, the area under cultivation decreased from five thousand thirty hectares in 2007 to four thousand eight hundred and eighty hectares in 2008, a reduction of approximately 7.9%. The total production also declined from eleven thousand six hundred and sixty metric tonnes to ten thousand seven hundred and ninety metric tonnes, a decrease of about 7.5%, while yield remained almost constant with a slight increase from 2.20 metric tonnes per hectare in 2007 to 2.21 metric tonnes per hectare of land in 2008, a marginal gain of 0.45%. However, from 2007 to 2008, there was a reduction in both the area cultivated and total rice production, but yield per hectare stayed virtually unchanged. This indicates that productivity levels were maintained despite cultivating less land, possibly due to stable farming efficiency or consistent agricultural inputs.²⁷

The data from 2009 to 2010 above represents agricultural statistics for rice (paddy) cultivated for two consecutive years covering area cultivated, total production, and yield per hectare. From 2009, nine thousand one hundred and seventy hectares were cultivated with production at sixteen thousand three hundred and twenty metric tonnes, yielding 1.78 metric tonnes per hectare. While, in 2010, twelve thousand four hundred and seventy hectares—an increase of about 36% more than in 2009—were cultivated. However, production doubled down to thirty-four thousand two hundred and ten metric tonnes, about a 110% increase, and the yield jumped to 2.74 metric tonnes per hectare of land, showing a 54% increase in efficiency. This suggests major improvements in farming practices or inputs, possibly government or private interventions, better climatic or water conditions, and the use of high-yielding seed varieties or technologies. Therefore, from 2009 to 2010, rice farming became more productive and efficient. Not only was more land brought under cultivation, but each hectare of land produced significantly more rice.²⁸

Meanwhile, thirteen thousand four hundred and forty hectares were cultivated in 2011, while nine thousand eight hundred and thirty hectares were cultivated in 2012. In 2011, rice production amounted to thirty thousand four hundred and thirty metric tonnes, while, in 2012, it dropped to twenty thousand twenty metric tonnes; a 34.2% decrease in total production was recorded. Therefore, yield dropped from 2.27 metric tonnes per hectare in 2011 to 2.04 metric tonnes per hectare in 2012, about a 10.1% decrease in yield. The drop in area under cultivation directly contributed to the decline in total production. However, productivity per hectare also declined, suggesting possible issues such as decreased in land cultivated, poor weather conditions, pests or diseases.²⁹

Table 4: Rice Production from 2013-2018

S/N	Crop	Year	Area (HA) '000	Production (MT) '000	Yield (MT/HA)
17	Rice (Paddy)	2013	9.97	20.25	2.03
18	Rice (Paddy)	2014	10.36	19.16	1.96
19	Rice (Paddy)	2015	89.00	174.00	1.94
20	Rice (Paddy)	2016	12.18	23.51	1.83
21	Rice (Paddy)	2017	13.48	24.24	1.87
22	Rice (Paddy)	2018	13.02	26.97	1.89

Source: Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, 2024.

The table above explains the area of land cultivated, rice production, and yield of rice crop. The total area cultivated in 2013 was nine thousand nine hundred and seventy hectares, with ten thousand three hundred and sixty hectares cultivated in 2014. Despite the increase in area, the total rice production decreased from twenty thousand two hundred fifty metric tonnes in 2013 to nineteen thousand one hundred and sixty metric tonnes in 2014. The overall crop yield (productivity per hectare) dropped from 2.03 metric tonnes per hectare in 2013 to 1.96 metric tonnes per hectare in 2014. Although more land was used for rice farming in 2014, the overall output decreased, indicating a decline in productivity due to various factors such as unfavourable weather, poor input quality like seeds or fertilisers, and pest/disease outbreaks.³⁰

²⁷ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Eleven Priority crops*. Lafia: NADP PME Department: 2024, 1.

²⁸ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Production Figure for Rice production in Doma LGA*. Lafia: NADP PME Department: 2024, 1.

²⁹ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, "Production Figure for Rice production" ...1.

³⁰ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Eleven Priority crops*. Lafia: NADP PME Department: 2024, 4.

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In 2015, eighty-nine thousand hectares were cultivated and the area under cultivation dropped to twelve thousand one hundred and eighty hectares in 2016. The production level in 2015 stands at one hundred and seventy-four thousand metric tonnes, while the production level in 2016 fell to twenty-three thousand five hundred and ten metric tonnes. As shown above, yield continued its downward trend, falling to 1.83 metric tonnes per hectare, the lowest in the four-year span, that is, from 2013 to 2016. By these, 2015 appears to be an outlier in terms of area and production, suggesting a large-scale government programmes and irrigation expansion. The dramatic changes between 2015 and 2016 suggest either inconsistent data collection/reporting or major shifts in policy, climate, or farmer preferences is responsible.³¹

Furthermore, in 2017, thirteen thousand four hundred and eighty hectares were cultivated with a production rate of twenty-four thousand two hundred and forty metric tonnes. Similarly, in 2018, thirteen thousand twenty hectares were cultivated with a production rate of twenty-six thousand nine hundred and seventy metric tonnes. A decrease in yield of 1.87 metric tonnes per hectare was recorded in 2017, while an increase in yield of 1.89 metric tonnes per hectare was recorded in 2018. An insight drawn from above is that, even though less land was used in 2018, production increased, indicating better productivity. The improvement in yield suggests enhanced farming practices, better inputs, or favourable growing conditions despite a decrease in land hectares.³²

Table 5: Rice Production from 2019-2023

S/N	Crop	Year	Area (HA) '000	Production (MT) '000	Yield (MT/HA)
23	Rice (Paddy)	2019	16.00	49.00	3.00
24	Rice (Paddy)	2020	20.80	74.09	3.56
25	Rice (Paddy)	2021	24.35	104.30	4.28
26	Rice (Paddy)	2022	24.83	107.40	4.33
27	Rice (Paddy)	2023	28.96	130.01	4.49

Source: Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, 2024.

The table five above indicates that sixteen thousand hectares of land were cultivated in 2019; likewise, twenty thousand eighty hectares were cultivated in 2020, showing a 30% increase in area under rice cultivation. In 2019, rice production was forty-nine thousand metric tonnes, while in 2020, it rose to seventy-four thousand ninety metric tonnes, which is a 51.02%. The table further shows that, yield improved significantly from 3.00 metric tonnes per hectare in 2019 to 3.56 metric tonnes per hectare in 2020, indicating enhanced productivity likely due to better farming practices, inputs, or favourable weather.³³

In 2021, land under rice cultivation increased steadily each year, from twenty-four thousand three hundred and fifty hectares, in 2012, twenty-four thousand eight hundred and thirty hectares were cultivated. Also, twenty-eight thousand nine hundred and sixty hectares were in 2023. This leads to a significant rise in rice production from one hundred and four thousand thirty metric tonnes in 2021 to one hundred and seven thousand forty metric tonnes in 2022 and one hundred and thirty thousand ten metric tonnes in 2023, a 24.6% increase over three years. Yield increased from 4.28 metric tonnes per hectare in 2021 to 4.33 metric tonnes in 2022 and 4.49 metric tonnes per hectare in 2023. Overall, the data shows positive trends in rice cultivation, efficiency, and output over the observed period, suggesting better farming practices, improved seed quality, or favourable climatic conditions.³⁴

Importance of Rice to Doma Communities

Rice is a staple food in Nigeria, consumed by people of all ages and socio-economic backgrounds. In Doma communities, rice is mostly used in celebrations, traditions, and as local cuisine, symbolising hospitality, generosity, and community bonding. Rice is also used as an offering or gift in Doma culture, depicting its cultural significance. In addition, rice plays a significant role in Doma cuisine and culture, with various local uses across different communities of hundreds of people who depend on rice for improving nutritional status and health.

Not only are more calories obtained worldwide from rice than from any other grain. Rice is also the major source of livelihood of small farmers and agricultural labour households in Doma local government, where at least two-thirds of arable land is planted to rice. Because of the economic and political importance of rice in Doma, no government has left its domestic policy unfavourable to rice production. Meanwhile, maintaining a stable domestic rice price for both consumers and producers is a separate and equally important concern. Moreover, given the political importance of rice and the instability of the rice market, most farmers aim for rice self-sufficiency rather than relying on interstate trade to pursue their food security goals.³⁵

³¹ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Eleven Priority crops*. Lafia: NADP PME Department: 2024, 5.

³² Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Nasarawa State Crop Production 1996-2023*. NADP: 2024, 8.

³³ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Production...5*.

³⁴ Nasarawa Agricultural Development Programme, *Production...6*.

³⁵ C. David Cristina, and J. Huang. "Political Economy of Rice Price Protection in Asia." *Journal of Economic Development and Cultural Change* vol.44 no. 3 (1996): 63-83.

Like other traditional dishes, one of the traditional rice dishes includes fried rice (Ishikapa kwanokwano) and Jollof rice (Ishikapa Gubobo), a one-pot rice dish flavoured with tomatoes, chili peppers, and spices, mostly served at social gatherings and celebrations such as traditional marriages, naming ceremonies, birthday celebrations, children's graduation parties, send-off parties, conferences, and political campaigns. Samuel describes the wide acceptability of rice when he said, "Alago and Agatu in Doma used rice to produce 'pap' (Ogwo gishipa), and 'rice food,' called Onagishikapa in Agatu, To-Owere in Bassa and Tuwon Shinkafa in Hausa, a traditional dish made from boiled rice, commonly consumed in northern Nigeria, is also consumed in Doma when women give birth." The local 'Pap' (Ogwo gishipa), is used to entertain visitors coming to show hospitality to the mother and the new baby. Also, it serves as a source of milk production to the nursing mother, mostly mixed with sesame. Ogah avers that farmers benefited significantly from rice in farming season considering its fastest and easiest way of cooking when everyone is hungry after working for a long time in the field. In addition, fried rice is a popular dish made with vegetables and meat or seafood. Over time, some traditional dishes mentioned above are products of borrowed ideas from different parts of the country and were later domesticated. Like coconut rice, a flavourful dish cooked with coconut milk and spices became popular among various communities in Doma Local Government over time.³⁶

Rice is used to make non-alcoholic beverages, mostly consumed as an appetiser or breakfast drink, either in the morning, afternoon or evening. Jonathan describes how rice is used to make various local snacks, such as rice cakes and fried rice balls called Akpakpa, Gangaya, Umu and Onmonmo in Alago and Agatu, when he states that rice flour is mixed with water and sesame and wrapped in fresh leaves, later heated with fire to make the needed product for consumption. Furthermore, rice flour is used in baking and cooking, particularly for people with gluten intolerance.³⁷

Deborah, a rice business tycoon, told of how businesses in rice generate more income as compared to other staples. She states that rice bought and stored for profit making in August at forty thousand naira could be sold in June-July of the following year at ninety thousand naira. She further argues that a 50 kg bag of parboiled rice sells for around ₦80,000, while local rice costs ₦120,000 for a sack of 40 mudus except now that the price dropped. In comparison, a bag of millet costs ₦58,000, and beans cost ₦75,000 for a 50 kg bag. She went further to authoritatively say that only pepper and melon are the two crops to reward high interest if stored.³⁸

Rice is widely consumed, with many local brands offering affordable and nutritious options and has moderate protein content, ranging from 6.72% to 6.93% in different rice varieties. Although beans are a good source of protein and essential minerals like iron and zinc. However, other staples like garri and millet have varying nutritional profiles, with garri being high in carbohydrates and millet being a good source of fibre and minerals but rice provides moderate protein content.³⁹

As outlined in the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan 2017-2020, rice production not only increases and contributes to the GDP but also creates a series of economic activities along the value chains of each agricultural product, with an emphasis on storage. One of the correspondents Adikwu in an interview posits that, rice creates national, regional, sub-regional, state and local trade. He went further to said, over five hundred stores were built and allocated for rice storage in Doma market. Each of the stores have over one thousand bags of rice for future sales and each store had over five to ten store keepers paid monthly for providing adequate security.⁴⁰ This practice has recruited massive youth into employment hub reducing active numbers in idleness. In addition, C. David Cristina and J. Huang corroborates that, there has been increase accompanied by a surge in the establishment of rice-producing and processing industries of different scales for the transformation of paddy rice to the form acceptable to consumers. The engagement of youth in paddy rice trade has also reduced unemployment rate of the areas under study.⁴¹

Rice milling, a crucial step in the post-production of rice, is the process of removing the husk and bran layers to produce an edible, white rice kernel that is sufficiently milled and free of impurities. Rice forms the basic primary processed product obtained from paddies, and this is further processed to obtain various secondary and tertiary products. Rice processing is an important activity in the rice value chain. Rice milling has ushered a lot of young men and women to productive engagement in Doma. John, one of the interviewees argues that, after selling rice harvested from the farm, he is paid to parboil rice for further milling which through this engagement increased his personal saving from what he earned as wages. The problems associated with the milling of paddy rice according to him in the country are the major reason most Nigerians prefer imported rice, which is free of foreign material, to

³⁶ D. Kennedy. "The Importance of Rice." Available at <http://www.jstor.org>. Accessed on 16 June 2025.

³⁷ Ogah. Simon, Teacher and Rice Seller, Interview, Agbashi, 3 May, 2025.

³⁸ Ose Deborah, Rice Seller, Interview, Doma, July 7, 2009.

³⁹ C. David Cristina, and J. Huang. "Political Economy of Rice Price Protection in Asia." *Journal of Economic Development and Cultural Change* Vol.44 No. 3 (1996): 83.

⁴⁰ Adikwu Moses Interview, Civil Servant Rtd in his Residence, Lafia, Nasarawa State, May 22th, 2025.

⁴¹ C. David Cristina, and J. Huang. "Political Economy of Rice ...463

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the local rice. Like any other economic activity, the sustainability of rice milling businesses hinges on the need to make a profit that reflects the existing economic reality in terms of the value of money in order to consistently offset the capital outlay.⁴²

CONCLUSION

The recent upsurge in rice production in Doma local government area is attributed to several factors. One, the presence of Olam company in the local government, cultivating over 10,000 hectares is responsible for high production rate. Two, the introduction and establishment of 'Olam nucleus out growers' scheme' attracting subsidies on the cost of improved seed variety, training i.e. knowledge transfers on various aspects of rice production and agricultural best practices, and extension services is another factor. Three, the rise of farm settlements in different locations of the local government such as Agbanoko, Omadugu, Samunaka, Baki-Kasa, and Ajewoni attracting migrant labours from different part of the country seeking for paid labours is another factor. Lastly, the introduction and adequate application of agro-allied chemicals such as fertilisers and herbicides of different kinds in providing essential nutrients, enhancing soil fertility and promoting healthy crop growth, leading to higher yields and the uses of course to control weeds, preventing competition for water and nutrients, resulting in better quality rice.

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3	Arron Jatau	Male	57 Years	Doma Lower Benue Office	5/11/2024
4	Bala J. Ewuga	Male	57 year	Lafia	16/2/2025.
5	Ogah Simon	Male	59 Years	Doma	7/7/2025
6	Ose Deborah	Male	58 Years	Agbashi	3/5/2025
7	Paul Anza	Male	54 years	Igbabo	15/11/2025.
8	Williams Akwashiki	Male	80 Years	Doma	14/11/2024

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